

FORTE-VLC: A Forward Tracing Self-Error Correction Variable Length Code for Image Coding in Wireless Application*

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ABSTRACT

Variable length code (VLC), also called Huffman code [1], is the most popular data compression technique used for solving transmission channel bandwidth bottleneck in image compression standards such as JPEG, MPEG, and H263. But, it is vulnerable to loss of synchronization if they are transmitted consecutively through a noisy wireless channel. It will result in large drops in transmission quality. We propose a novel VLC coding/decoding scheme, which has high error resilient and correction capability. It uses prefix-suffix coding structure and redundant bits for error tracing and correction. We called it as **Forward Tracing Self-Error Correction VLC (FORTE-VLC)**. It provides high tolerances to random and burst errors in worsening channel conditions. In addition, it exhibits high synchronization capability. Simulation result shows that it can achieve 82% of error correction and 91% of synchronization capability for MPEG B.15 VLC table. It also achieves higher picture quality (PSNR=29.5dB) compared to existing VLC schemes at bit error rate (BER) of 10^{-3} environment. Finally, we present related codec architecture. It is very suitable and efficient for VLSI implementation. It has the advantage of low memory requirement and high throughput rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Variable length code (VLC), which has minimal redundancy for a given data source has widely been used in digital image compression standards such as JPEG, MPEG and H.263. This is achieved by non-uniform occurrence probability distribution of symbols. By coding a frequently occurred symbol to a shorter code and coding a code seldom occurred to a longer code will make the average code length less than coding symbol to a fixed-length code (FLC). As a result, it achieves data compression and more efficient in reducing the bit rate than FLC.

Although VLC ensures optimal coding, it is highly sensitive to channel errors when VLCs are transmitted consecutively through noisy wireless channel. Because of variable length coding scheme, any bit error occurs during transmission will propagate an unknown distance until it is resynchronization as shown in Fig. 1. In practice, errors may propagate a considerable period and lose dozen of words before synchronization is re-established. In the past, many techniques are proposed to add redundant bits for

error detection and error correction to ensure the correctness of transmitted data. It will sacrifice some channel bandwidth, which is very valuable in some applications. As a result, it is important to develop one coding scheme, which can achieve both data compression and error correction capability for wireless application. Therefore, designing VLC that is robust against channel noise and can easily recover synchronization once it has been lost is important for image transmission over wireless channel. We propose a novel VLC coding scheme, called FORTE-VLC, which has good tolerance to random and burst errors in worsening channel conditions. It exhibits high synchronization, error correction capability and low average code length.

Figure 1 : Error propagation of VLC

The organization of the paper is as follows. In section 2, we first introduce the idea and coding structure of FORTE-VLC. Then, we will discuss and analyze FORTE-VLC error correction mechanism and capability. Section 3 will present related FORTE-VLC codec architecture design. Finally, simulation results and performance comparisons are provided in section 4. We will give a conclusion in section 5.

2. CONSTRUCTING FORTE-VLC

2.1 The Idea and Structure of FORTE-VLC

An error occurring in VLC bitstream as well as a decoder malfunction can lead to a loss of synchronization, which in turn can result in the insertion or deletion of symbols at the decoder and cause error propagation. But, the synchronization capability needs an additional requirement for a code that leads to a loss of efficiency in terms of average codeword length. In fact, apart

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from trivial cases, no optimal binary code is synchronizable [2]. Therefore, it is interesting to consider codes able for self-synchronization. Many researchers [3] – [11] have studied the ability of VLC code to synchronize and tried to overcome the low error resilient problem. But, most of these proposed schemes only focus on resynchronization capability or reducing the error propagation distance when error is detected. They limit the error in a small region, but didn't have error detection and correction capability. As a result, we propose FORTE-VLC, which sacrifice a bit of compression ratio and use advanced decoding mechanism to gain high error correction capability. It is an effective coding scheme for using in bandwidth-limited channel where data correctness is an important issue.

The degree of quality degradation due to VLC loss of synchronization strongly depends on error position and coding table characteristics. We present a novel FORTE-VLC constructed by prefix-suffix coding structure as shown in Fig. 2. In other words, each codeword of FORTE-VLC is combined by two parts of code, fixed length prefix code (FLPC) and variable length suffix code (VLSC).

Figure 2 : FORTE-VLC Coding Structure

FLPC is 5 bits and consists of two parts, group code (GC) and check code (CC). The relation between GC and CC is EXOR operation shown in Fig. 2. It is almost similar to Hamming coding scheme. But, FLPC can only use CC to correct one bit error happened in GC. If the error is happened in CC, FLPC can't detect and correct it. So, this GC protection scheme is called as reducing Hamming relationship (REHS). Only FLPC with correct REHS is valid FLPC (VFLPC). We will propose an effective decoding mechanism to overcome this weak point later. Of course, we can insert more redundant bits into CC for achieving one bit error correction capability at any bit location of FLPC. But, it will reduce coding efficiency.

For error happened in VLSC, it will resulting in decoding wrong symbol within the same group. No error will be propagated to next codeword. But, VLSC doesn't have any error correction capability since it uses all combinational patterns for coding. So FLPC needs to be designed for high error detection and correction (EDC) capability and VLSC has synchronization capability. Thus, FORTE-VLC will only have very small portion of probability to lose synchronization. Besides, channel burst error will be partitioned into FLPC and VLSC portions that will be easier for handling since the continuous error status has been broken. BBRT Re-synchronization mechanism, shown in Fig. 3, can be used to protect loss of synchronization when burst error is happened.

3 bits of GC can represent 8 group of codes. All codewords within one group have the same length of suffix code. As a result, GC determines the length of suffix code and aligns the codeword boundary. FLPC only uses 8 of 32 combinational patterns

because of REHS. But, VLSC can use all 2^n combinational patterns, where n is the length (variable) of VLSC. This coding structure provides high flexibility for large coding table and remains VLC prefix code condition. Another performance factor of FORTE-VLC is average code length (ACL). For MPEG B.15 VLC table, ACL of FLC is 7, Huffman code is 3, and FORTE-VLC is 5.6. Small ACL means it has higher data compression capability.

2.2 Error Correction Mechanism

As described in previous description, VLSC will not have error correction capability if we use all its valid patterns for coding. So, it is possible for VLSC having error correction capability. For error happened in FLPC, it may lead to lose synchronization. As a result, it is important for us to focus on FLPC error detection and correction mechanism as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: FORTE-VLC Error Correction Mechanism

We focus on single bit (random) error type, which is the most popular error situation in many applications and channels. If GC and CC of FLPC meet REHS checking, implying that FLPC contains no error and it is a VFLPC. Otherwise, violation of REHS checking means FLPC having error disturbance during transmission. We need to detect and correct it.

Group Code Error

We assume CC is correct and do GC error correction mechanism (GC-ECM). Thus, we can use received GC[2:0] to compute HR[1:0] using REHS equations. Then, HR is compared with received CC. The compared result can be used to correct GC as shown in Fig. 4. After that, we can know the group of current decoded symbol and determine the suffix code length. Consequently, it can align the codeword and get next FLPC for REHS checking. If it passes the REHS checking, it ensures the previous assumption (CC has no error) is correct. Otherwise, it indicates CC has error and GC-ECM becomes fails. Thus, we need to do CC-ECM. Of course, next FLPC itself may have error. This will lead to wrong GC-ECM decision although we have already corrected current GC error. Fortunately, probability of two continuous GC errors is low.

Comp[1]	Comp[0]	Error Status and Correction
0	0	GC[1:0] correct, nothing wrong
0	1	GC[2] error, correct with inverting it
1	0	GC[0] error, correct with inverting it
1	1	GC[1] error, correct with inverting it

Received GC[2:0], CC[1:0] Compare HR and CC :
 $HR[0] = GC[2] \wedge GC[1]$ $Comp[0] = HR[0] \wedge CC[0]$
 $HR[1] = GC[1] \wedge GC[0]$ $Comp[1] = HR[1] \wedge CC[1]$

Figure 4: GC Correction Scheme

Check Code Error

For correct GC and CC has error, we need to do CC error correction mechanism (CC-ECM). It simply ignores CC and use GC to align the codeword and get next FLPC for REHS checking. If it satisfies REHS, then CC is likely to be the error source. Thus, we can use REHS equation to regenerate correct CC. For next FLPC which doesn't meet REHS, it indicates loss of synchronization. BBRT-RS is required to achieve re-synchronization. There are 8 error patterns of 32 combinational patterns that can also satisfy REHS. As a result, it has still 25% probability of wrong CC-ECM operation. GC-ECM and CC-ECM can be performed concurrently. But, the GC-ECM result has high priority than CC-ECM since GC is more sensitive (longer length) to noise.

Burst Error

Burst error will cause loss of synchronization since both CC-ECM and GC-ECM will become failed. Besides, two continuous FLPC errors and wrong ECM decision will also result in the same situation. Although simulation results show that probability of these situations is low, we perform bit-by-bit REHS test for re-synchronization (BBRT-RS). BBRT-RS becomes successful when it finds two consecutive VFLPC. It is only about 6% ($1/4 \times 1/4 = 1/16$) probability for re-synchronization at wrong position. Otherwise, it can be correctly re-synchronized between two codewords. Thus, it achieves high synchronization capability.

FORTE-VLC coding structure and ECM ensure high error correction (EC) and error synchronization (ES) capabilities for random codeword having one bit error.

VLSC: 100% SC, no EC; GC: 100% SC and EC; CC: 75% SC and EC. As a result, each codeword has $EC = (3+2 \times 0.75)/n$ and $ES = (3+2 \times 0.75+i)/n$ where n and i are codeword and VLSC length respectively. Applying FORTE-VLC to MPEG B.15 VLC table ($i: 0 \sim 6$), it can reach 82% EC and 91% ES capabilities.

3. FORTE-VLC CODEC ARCHITECTURE

In order to meet diverse applications and standard-defined tables, designed codec system requires programmability to load various VLC tables without redesign the hardware. Constant processing rate is also an important design issue for reducing the I/O interface complexity and achieving high throughput rate that is required in real time application. The proposed FORTE-VLC codec system can achieve these performances and targets. From previous section, we note that FORTE-VLC table has group characteristic, which is constructed by 8 groups of codeword with the same codeword length. Based on efficient memory mapping strategy, encoding and decoding processes can be completed by applying numerical properties and simple arithmetic operations. Related memory requirement can also be optimized. Block diagram of the proposed FORTE-VLC codec system is shown in Fig. 5. It consists of two parts: encoder and decoder architecture.

Figure 5: Block diagram of FORTE-VLC codec system

For encoding, the encoding symbol will be compared with each group base address (i.e. first symbol of each group) in parallel. Then, related group information, base address, and VLSC length, can be read out. ALU will calculate the difference between encoding symbol and relative base address. This offset value will form VLSC code. Also, code mixer will generate GC and CC. Then, code mixer will concatenated them to form FORTE-VLC bitstream. For decoding, STP interface FIFO will shift-and-align decoding bitstream relative to decoding result. It is also used to buffer and synchronize between input data and system decoding rate. The CC-ECM and GC-ECM will correct the existence single bit error and fetching related group base address and VLSC length. Then, VLSC (offset) will be extracted from bitstream and summed with base address forming symbol address. Finally, it accesses SSRAM-ST and output the decoded symbol. When it lost synchronization, BBRT-RS will be activated to search next synchronization location.

The stored information of each group is only group base address and VLSC length. For 256 symbols table, base address needs 8 bits and VLSC length is 3 bits. As a result, it only requires 88 bits (8×11) memory space for storing FORTE-VLC table information. The required memory space is much less than

traditional memory-based VLC codec system. Finally, FORTE-VLC codec system can operate at 3V power supply with clock rate up to 133MHz, using 0.35um CMOS technology. Thus, 133M-symbol throughput rate can be achieved.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to examine the effectiveness and performance of FORTE-VLC for practical applications, we have simulated the Lena image (512x512, 256-level grayscale). We use FORTE-VLC and Huffman code to encode each pixel grayscale value and run/level symbol. Then, we compare FORTE-VLC and Huffman coding result at bit error rate (BER) of 10^{-3} , as shown in Fig. 6. It shows that FORTE-VLC has an excellent performance improvement. Both coding schemes are also simulated for a range of BER. Peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) at various bit error rates is shown in Fig.7(pixel) and Fig.8(DCT-block). PSNR of FORTE-VLC is about 15dB better than Huffman code averagely. It indicates FORTE-VLC having good error correction capability.

Figure 6: Simulation result with end of line synchronization codeword and 0.1% BER.

5. CONCLUSION

Video transmission over error-prone wireless communication channels requires higher error resiliency than required in other channels. We propose a novel forward tracing self-error correction VLC (FORTE-VLC) coding scheme. It gives high tolerances to random and burst errors in worsening channel conditions and exhibits high error correction and synchronization capabilities. Simulation result shows that it achieves high signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR=29.5dB) compared to traditional VLC schemes at bit error rate (BER) of 10^{-3} environment. It enhances the PSNR and image quality effectively, which is 15dB higher than Huffman coding averagely. Moreover, the proposed FORTE-VLC codec architecture is very suitable for VLSI implementation, especially for its low memory requirement and high throughput rate.

Figure 7: Variation of PSNR with BER (Pixel-based)

Figure 8: Variation of PSNR with BER (DCT-block-based)

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